

Representation of Regions for Accurate Motion Compensation

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ABSTRACT

We propose a novel motion compensation technique for the precise reconstruction of regions over several frames within a region-based coding scheme. This is achieved by using a more accurate internal representation of arbitrarily shaped regions than the standard grid structure, thus avoiding repeated approximations for a region at each frame.

1 INTRODUCTION

Image sequence coding has become widely acknowledged as a means of enabling several *multimedia* applications [3, 1]. Current efforts in the research community are being channelled towards region-based video compression which are expected to provide a good quality image at a low bitrate as well as content-based manipulation, scalability and editing of the image sequence. One of the components of this type of codec, i.e. the motion compensation of arbitrarily-shaped objects, is the subject of this paper.

During the process of reconstruction of individual frames of a video sequence, regions which undergo non-integer motion have to be mapped back to an integer grid, for example by a bilinear interpolation operation. Other reconstruction kernels have been used within the *Image Processing* community [2]. Analysis in the frequency domain showed that all the interpolation kernels (e.g. linear, quadratic, Catmull-Rom cubic) have some low-pass filtering property. Repeated application of such a filter can degrade picture quality to a significant extent. Our proposed technique prevents repeated loss of high frequency information by keeping a representation of the original region, from which a grid representation can be derived whenever required.

In the next section, we describe why regions undergo smoothing due to repeated compensation. In section 3, a novel region representation is presented which avoids smoothing and thus wastage of bits. The manipulation of the data structure at different stages is also described in detail. We then provide comparative results in section 4 for individual regions and for complete sequences.

2 EXPLANATION OF SMOOTHING DUE TO SUCCESSIVE INTERPOLATIONS

In this section we show that, as frames get reconstructed by a region-based codec, the smoothing effects due to interpolation do build up. The type of region-based codec we have used is similar to the one presented by Yokoyama *et al* [4]. The initial set of regions in the scene is created by segmentation on the decoded intra image on both sides of the codec to avoid sending expensive contour information. Changes to the regions are detected at the encoder side and are communicated to the decoder. These include motion vector and prediction error information. The conventional structure for storing region information is an image of the texture content of the region with its associated alpha map, which is also image-based. In natural image sequences, regions sometimes undergo non-integer motion. However, an integer grid-based representation has to be created for two distinct purposes: firstly for viewing and secondly for serving as reference for the next frame. The integer grid-based image is obtained by spatial interpolation, e.g. bilinear interpolation, which implies low-pass filtering.

To simulate successive interpolation operations for a simple one-dimensional signal (fig 1), values at intermediate sampling positions are calculated, after which the original samples are discarded - which is what happens in a video compression system with a grid-based interpolation of regions. As can be seen the signal gets smoother and smoother. In a video compression system, this means that a significant amount of high frequency information appears in the prediction error image, thus decreasing compression efficiency.

3 MOTION COMPENSATION FROM AN ACCURATE INTERNAL REPRESENTATION

Sizeable savings in bitrate at a given quality can be achieved if a region representation is used which does not allow information previously available to the decoder to be thrown away by successive interpolations. Such a representation is one which keeps individual points of

Figure 1: Filtering effect on a block of samples due to successive applications of an interpolation filter

Figure 2: Manipulation of internal data structure for regions

a region together with their associated intensity values independent of a grid structure, i.e.

$$R' = \{(\tilde{x}_i, \tilde{p}_i) | i = 1 \dots M; x_i \in \mathbb{R}^2\}. \quad (1)$$

We call this a floating point representation because the pixel positions are allowed to take floating point values. An image can be built from this representation for viewing purposes, after which the interpolated regions are never used. The interpolated regions are not kept as a reference for the next frame. This means that the smoothing effect does not accumulate.

The content of the region has to be updated, for example in cases of illumination variations or inadequate motion representation. The error image is calculated at the encoder and transmitted using a transform-based technique. The error values are available at the grid points, whereas the error values at the compensated points are needed to update the region representation. An interpo-

Figure 3: Bitrate comparison for H.263 test sequences

lation from the neighbouring error values is thus needed for each point belonging to the region. The resulting error value is then added to the available value. Some smoothing of the image does occur but the interpolation is only done once on each error image and does not cause much accumulation of error.

4 RESULTS

Results on the *Calendar125* sequence are presented. For a skip size of 1, the motion of the object is in the range of 0.3 - 0.7 pixels. This is the range where the smoothing effect due to bilinear interpolation is most noticeable. The quantization step was 16 for both the Inter and Intra modes. A motion vector quantization step size of 0.1 was used because accurate motion measurement is also needed in order for the novel motion compensation algorithm to be most effective. Fortunately, the estimation of the motion of regions containing a large amount of texture can be done accurately. Thus good motion measurements can be exploited whenever they can be obtained. The quantized motion vectors were coded losslessly. The interpolation techniques tried for the grid representation of regions were the bilinear and biquadratic ones.

It can be observed from figure 6 that the proposed technique substantially outperforms both types of interpolation on a standard grid structure both in terms of bitrate and PSNR. It is also interesting to note that biquadratic interpolation actually provides limited benefit with respect to bilinear interpolation. The improvement in performance depends on the amount of sub-pixel motion and intricate texture for each region.

The frequency of occurrence of above-mentioned regions will be one determining factor for the magnitude of the overall improvement when coding a whole image sequence. The significance of using an internal floating point representation for all the regions within a natural image sequence will now be assessed. It will also be

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: Comparison of motion compensated error (a)with and (b)without floating point representation for frame number 8 of the *Calendar125* sequence

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Comparison of number of bits spent per block (a)with and (b)without floating point representation for frame number 8 of the *Calendar125* sequence

Figure 6: Improvement for the *Calendar125* sequence using the floating point representation

possible to provide a comparison with the performance achieved by a block-based system.

Experiments were carried out on image sequences from the H.263 test set (figure 3). The use of the floating point representation is found to produce a lower bitrate compared to the standard bilinear interpolation for the majority of the sequences. The PSNR was similar for both techniques. The exceptions were the *Bream*, *Bus150* and *Foreman* sequences, for which the block-based codec is still superior mainly because of the imperfect segmentation in our region based codec. A considerable improvement in the quality of motion compensation for the *Calendar125* image sequence in particular was observed. Figures 5(a) and 5(b) demonstrate the relative number of bits spent in coding the motion compensated error image for frame 8 (the intensity of each block is proportional to the number of bits required to code the block). Figure 4 shows the corresponding motion compensated error images. In the upper portion of the image, which contains highly-textured objects moving at sub-pixel accuracy, fewer bits are used for the case of the floating point representation. Savings are also made for the chrominance channels which contain high frequency information for this particular sequence. Large errors occur in both cases in all the blocks where

the region description does not model the scene well enough, i.e. at motion boundaries. In the lower portion of the image, which contains objects which cannot be easily modelled with planar patches, the bitrate is similar in both cases.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated the smoothing effect for certain regions due to successive interpolation operations inherent in region-based codecs. A novel representation as well as the way to update regions, should their content vary, was proposed. The use of the floating point representation of regions was seen to be advantageous for most of the natural image sequences in the H.263 test set. In certain cases the coding efficiency of the region-based coding has been brought up to that of the block-based technique while the former also provides the added advantage of enabling content-based functionality.

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